

Greater	Category	Example Images UVP	Reference	Descriptors	Additional Notes
Cyanobacteria	Trichodesmium			<p>Critical Criteria: 1/3 shapes required Three shapes: BOWTIES, PUFFS, TUFTS PUFFS: Filamentous (lines which diverge along multiple vectors) sphere without a definitive perimeter separating outer filaments and interior density. BOWTIES: Filaments of similar mean grey level converging on a central axis. Overall shape that of two triangles which overlap at one vertice TUFTS: Thin ovals that converge to a lighter mean grey level at the ends. Can be bent or straight with constriction at the midway point. Supplemental Descriptors: Depth likely: 0-200m Possibly Confused with: Acantharia - have fewer and more rigid podia which are paired across its central axis Foraminifera - defined border between central mass and filamentous podia Fecal Pellets - Blunt ends without a convergence to a lighter mean grey level at the ends. No filamentous separation of strands.</p>	
Crustacea	Eumalacostraca			<p>Critical Criteria: Photophores - dense repeating circles on ventral side of the organism (often seen) Dense eye pairs - high mean grey level spheres Fusiform silhouette Splayed uropod and / or telson - not always visible rostrum - not always visible Antennae / antennula present Separation of the segmented carapace - Visible as pattern of parallel dorsal lines. Important identifier when present Supplemental Descriptors: Presence of thoracic legs or pleopods Possibly Confused with: none</p>	
	Copepod			<p>Critical Descriptors: 2/3 required Antennae pair - size and length variable but perpendicular to the longitudinal axis of the organism Fusiform silhouette - visible from orientations which capture the longitudinal axis Urosome - thinner section following a constriction located distally relative to the prosome but on the same longitudinal axis Supplemental Descriptors: periopods - rarely visible, possible to see from side view eggs sacs - below or beside lower urosome / metasome Possibly Confused with: Ostracods - antennae shorter and not perpendicular to longitudinal axis, more spherical and absent of urosome. Appendages shorter relative to overall size when visible</p>	
	Luciferidae			<p>Critical Criteria: Dense stalked eye pairs - paired spheres of high mean grey level attached to thin extensions perpendicular to longitudinal axis. Stretched fusiform silhouette - visible from the side Presence of thoracic legs or pleopods - thoracic legs often visible. Lines descending perpendicular to longitudinal axis. Supplemental Info: Antennae / antennula present - thin and long (can be 1/2 body size) when visible Splayed uropod and / or telson - rarely visible but more dense than other organismal structures when imaged Possibly Confused with: none</p>	
	Ostracods			<p>Critical Criteria: 2/3 Required Nearly spherical or oval silhouette Small antennae or splayed appendages - less than 1/3 organismal length Hinge - High mean grey level line down the ventral side of the organism Rostrum - notch at the top of the organism present on one end only Supplemental Descriptors: Can be binary in density between a less and more dense interior section Possibly Confused with: Copepods -Fusiform silhouette, perpendicular antennae, urosome present</p>	

Greater	Category	Example Images UVP	Reference	Descriptors	Additional Notes
	Rhizaria (BROAD)			<p>Critical Criteria: 2 concentric circles Exterior circle's perimeter is mostly uninterrupted and smooth Interior circle is a higher mean grey level than exterior circle Possibly confused with: none</p>	
	Foraminifera			<p>Critical Criteria: Circular central mass - very dark / high mean grey level, with a well defined circular perimeter which is smooth Podia are at least as long as the central circle - terminal end of podia not always visible due to decreasing mean grey level Filamentous (lines which diverge along multiple vectors) podia are not rigid extensions. Supplemental Descriptors: Overlapping spheres at the center of the organism - rarely visible due to high mean grey level of central circle Possibly Confused with: Trichodesmium - no circular central perimeter / no distinguishing perimeter between filaments and central sphere</p>	
Rhizaria	Colodaria			<p>Critical Criteria: 1/2 shapes required Two shapes - COLONIAL and SOLITARY COLONY and SOLITARY both require an identifiable perimeter that contains the 'dots' / circles interior to the organism COLONY - elongated cylinder or sphere with multiple points / small circles of high mean grey level SOLITARY - spherical shape with multiple dots of higher density and a large exterior halo with a gradient of lower mean grey level surrounding the higher mean grey level interior Supplemental Descriptors: Some colonies present with a 'pretzel' shape characteristic Possibly Confused with: Blur - does not have an identifiable perimeter or circles of high mean grey level Castinelidae (Phaeodaria) - lacks the larger halo that solitary colodaria possess and does not have the dots of higher density seen in colodaria</p>	
	Acantharia			<p>Critical Criteria: symmetrical spines / podia converging on a central axis there must be at least 3 spines / podia present (to rule out the possibility of a single filament overlapping a particle) spines / podia are thin, and uniform in mean grey level (sometimes appear slightly denser at their lateral end) spines / podia extend beyond the ectoplasm when ectoplasm is visible (to differentiate from other rhizaria in phaeodaria) rarely above 2.5mm in longest axis in observed samples Possibly Confused with: Phaeodaria - distinguished from phaeodaria by the symmetry of the spines around the ectoplasm (exterior circle)</p>	
	Phaeodaria			<p>Critical Criteria: Highly variable group, often requiring individual attention Exterior circle's perimeter is mostly uninterrupted Spines / Podia present - lines converging on the central axis of the organism Supplemental Descriptors: Highly variable group homogenous mean grey level within ectoplasm (exterior circle) might be denser around the edge of the ectoplasm (exterior circle) dense endoplasm / nucleus (interior circle) spines / podia rarely extend more than 1/3 body length beyond ectoplasm (when they do, high mean grey level at distal ends)</p>	

Greater	Category	Example Images UVP	Reference	Descriptors	Additional Notes
Bubbles	Bubbles			<p>Critical Criteria: primarily in the upper 20m of the water column ovals / spheres with high mean grey level crescents which bend along the perimeter suggesting a more complete circle Often blurry ovals with some distortion from a perfect sphere or oval Possibly Confused with: Foraminifera - high mean grey level and singular central circle, paired with the presence of filamentous podia</p>	
Diatoms	Diatom Mats		<p>Marine Plankton: Section 3, Part 1, Fig 14 By Claudia Castellani and Martin Edwards</p>	<p>Critical Criteria: Overlapping lattice of filaments Variable mean grey level in strips or striations Composed of many distinct filaments Often speckled with spots of higher mean grey level - do not display a pattern or consistent size Possible Confused with: Foraminifera - filamentous podia converge on a dark central circle with a defined perimeter Marine snow - lacks lattice of distinct filaments</p>	
Cnidaria	Siphonophore		<p>Marine Plankton: Section 3, Part 2, Fig 96 By Claudia Castellani and Martin Edwards</p>	<p>Critical Criteria: 2/3 required Cone shaped nectophore (Rarely seen) - has a radial canal or nectosac (sometimes visible) Siphosome present - chain of bracts with a central stem following a single longitudinal axis (often seen) Siphosome has an alternating mean grey level pattern in the shape of a stemmed sphere Possibly confused with: Doliolid (Old Nurse) - has parallel banding to the barrel of the body</p>	
Cnidaria	Cnidaria sp.		<p>Marine Plankton: Section 3, Part 2, Fig 33 By Claudia Castellani and Martin Edwards</p>	<p>Critical Criteria: Bell present - hemisphere with circular rim Aboral organ - Higher mean grey level than the surrounding bell, roughly central to the apex of the bell (Aboral pole) Marginal tentacles / Circular canals - higher mean grey level circle at oral pole, sometimes with filamentous projections along the circle (tentacles) Supplemental Descriptors: Radial symmetry when seen from above or below Presence of tentacles below the bell - variable in number, thickness and placement around the bell (not always seen) Possibly Confused with: none</p>	

Greater	Category	Example Images UVP	Reference	Descriptors	Additional Notes
Larval Fish	Larval Fish		<p>Critical Criteria: Dense eye pairs - high mean grey level spheres which are not stalked Presence of central chord Supplemental Descriptors: Tail sometimes present - sagittally played distal triangle Possibly Confused with: none</p>		
Annelid	Alciopid		<p>Critical Criteria: Long segmented body - repeating pattern of parapodia uniform in shape and mean grey level Large spherical eyes - at the proximal end of the thin wavy body shape Silhouette is non-rigid, exhibiting a wavy form Possibly Confused with: Tomopterid - no large eyes present, fusiform body with paddle shaped parapodia, cirriform appendage present</p>		
	Tomopterid	 Marine Plankton: Section 3, Part 2, Fig 346 By Claudia Castellani and Martin Edwards	<p>Critical Criteria: 2/3 required Repeating pairs of paddle shaped parapodia - biramous parapodia taper with body form towards the tail creating a fusiform silhouette Central body line Tail - thin extension (relative to body) at the distal end of the silhouette Supplemental Descriptors: Cirriform appendage sometimes visible - thin bar perpendicular to longitudinal axis Eyes seen as circles of low mean grey level (often not seen due to contrast) Ramus with rim and fleshy lobe (not always visible) Possibly confused with: Siphonore - alternating density chain is not in pairs, does not resemble podia, and lacks the taper toward the end of the body Alciopid - Telescopic large and dense eyes, lack elongated biramous parapodia, do not taper from a broad mid-body</p>		
Cheatoagnath	Cheatoagnath		<p>Critical Criteria: highmean grey level head - due to the presence of grasping spines on the side of the head (eyes usually not seen) Mean grey level transition between trunk and tail present Mostly rigid body form - will have no to moderate bend to overall silhouette (some permissible) Supplemental Descriptors: Seminal vesicles present on either side of the tail - highermean grey level spherical strcutures Fins (usually not seen, Anterior or Lateral fin, due to contrast) - present as thin crescents along side of the body Central gastric line (often visible) - line running longitudinally along organisms interior Possibly Confused with: Alciopid - Eyes are much larger and spherical (as compared to flatter chaeto grasping spines), podia present in repeating pattern down body no break between lower density trunk and higher density tail, no dark seminal vesicles, body form can be highly wavy</p>		
Mollusca	Gymnosomata	 Marine Plankton: Section 3, Part 2, Fig 356 By Claudia Castellani and Martin Edwards	<p>Critical Criteria: Elongated oval body with constrictions in the form of ciliary bands Symmetrical wing pairs present - slightly triangular Supplemental Descriptors: Proximal end of the body more blunt (head) with distal end more tapered Bilaterally symmetrical (not always visible given orientation) Possibly Confused with: none</p>		
	Cephalopod		<p>Critical Criteria: Fusiform / oval body shape - more elongated at times due to evasive movement and converging tentacles Smooth perimeter mantle - silhouette constriction apparent when progressing distally towards the head and tentacles Supplemental Descriptors: High mean grey level paired eyeparts - sometimes seen as darker spots somewhat central to the overall body, on opposite sides Possibly Confused with: none</p>		

Greater	Category	Example Images VVP	Reference	Descriptors	Additional Notes
Ctenophore	Ctenophore		<p>Critical Criteria:</p> <p>Barrel shape to silhouette - sometimes presents with tentacles as extended lines from one end of the barrel</p> <p>8 rows of ciliary combs can be seen as high mean grey level striations along the body form</p> <p>Supplemental Descriptors:</p> <p>Top down: radiating symmetrical striations of high mean grey level in a pattern</p> <p>Tentilla - thin filaments extending perpendicularly from the tentacles</p> <p>Possibly Confused with:</p> <p>Doliolids - will present with horizontal parallel banding, will not have vertical combs of higher mean grey level</p> <p>Salpida - will have horizontal banding (not parallel)</p>		
Unliving	Marine Aggregate		<p>Critical Criteria: Highly morphologically variable</p> <p>Uneven perimeter - interrupted perimeter which is not smooth</p> <p>Variable internal mean grey level - can be spotty, dotted or clumped with structures of high or low mean grey level</p> <p>non-patterened mean grey level - no symmetry or repeating structures</p> <p>Majority of the object being imaged is not blurry (a smooth transition from background mean grey level to higher mean grey level leaving open the possibility for existing structures at the background mean grey level)</p> <p>Supplemental Descriptors:</p> <p>Appears at all depths</p> <p>Possibly Confused with:</p> <p>Foraminifera - Will have a circular center with identifiable smooth perimeter, will have filaments that converge on a central axis, will not have random distributions of high mean grey level structures, unless entangled with marine snow (requiring individual attention)</p> <p>Diatom Mats - will have an overlapping lattice appearance</p>		
	Single Filament		<p>Critical Criteria:</p> <p>Elongated rectangles - sometimes sectioned with transverse lines of high mean grey level</p> <p>Can be rigid or wavy in structure</p> <p>Smooth and indetifiable perimeter</p> <p>Possibly confused with:</p> <p>Trichodesmium - has filaments which converge on a central axis and are more numerous and higher in mean grey level</p> <p>Fecal pellets - high mean grey level across length of the pellet with no variation in grey level pattern such as transverse striations</p>		
Tunicata	Appendicularia	 Marine Plankton: Section 3, Part 2, Fig 408 By Claudia Castellani and Martin Edwards	<p>Critical Criteria:</p> <p>(Body)</p> <p>Size on the order of 2-5 mm along longest axis in observed images</p> <p>Trunk - oval or club shaped portion perpendicular to tail, high mean grey level</p> <p>Tail - attached to the ventral section of the oval perpendicularly, often wavy and blade-like</p> <p>Notochord - runs the length of the tail, central line of higher density</p> <p>(House)</p> <p>Much larger (often on the order of tens of mm) and more common than the body of the organism</p> <p>Ribbed dual-lobed shape - highly transparent (low mean grey level) with higher mean grey level in the form of lateral ribbing</p> <p>Possibly Confused with:</p> <p>Ascidian larvae - tail is in parallel with their trunk, not perpendicular</p>		
	Doliolida		<p>Critical Criteria:</p> <p>Barrel shaped body - bands are parallel to one another, banding overall is perpendicular to the longitudinal axis of the body</p> <p>Posterior and Anterior barrel openings - cloacal siphon and oral siphon high in mean grey level</p> <p>Possibly Confused with:</p> <p>Salps - banding is not parallel</p> <p>Ctenophores - banding will present as 8 radially symmetrical combs, banding is lateral to the barrel of the body</p>		
	Salpidae		<p>Critical Criteria:</p> <p>Barrel shaped body - overall banding is perpendicular to the longitudinal axis of the organism, bands are not parallel to each other</p> <p>Posterior and Anterior openings - cloacal siphon and oral siphon high in mean grey level</p> <p>Possibly Confused with:</p> <p>Doliolid - has parallel banding</p>		